

Scaling Research Capacity Strengthening with Large Language Models: the potential of AI

Introduction

A quarter of a century ago the importance of health research capacity strengthening (RCS) was highlighted under the catchphrase of “the 10/90 gap”.^[1] It came from a realisation that research capacity in many low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) was woefully inadequate.^[2] In the pithy reframing, “the 10/90 gap” gave urgency to the problem that only 10% of the world’s health research was done in the countries, where 90% of preventable deaths happened and the greatest burden of infectious disease occurred.

Significant effort has been made in the past 25 years to improve research capacity, but it remains a substantial inequity, in no small part because of the challenge of scaling RCS.^[3–6]

Smaller, boutique, approaches to individual RCS remain popular, and have added considerably to the skills of health researchers in LMICs.^[4,5] Unfortunately, their scalability is limited by their very structure: in-person, intensive training in a high-income country. An important development, increasing access to research training globally, is the growing availability of massive open online courses (MOOCs), organised by a wide range of institutions. For example, the WHO hosted special programme, TDR, leads capacity strengthening in implementation research for infectious diseases of poverty, and provides, together with partners, a variety of general and advanced MOOCs.^[7,8] MOOCs are accessible by anyone with internet access, anywhere in the world. They have expanded the educational franchise and given thousands of people in LMICs the opportunity to develop their research skills.

The goal of RCS is for health researchers to be able to “... initiate and improve the quality of their research as well as absorb and translate existing tools for use in their own particular national contexts and also participate in generating new tools” (p.1702).^[9] Almost five decades on from the first focused steps in RCS,^[2] many LMICs still lack sufficient health research capacity to support national needs and support scientific independence. Boutique courses and MOOCs have helped, but they are not enough. A multitude of individual and systems challenges remain. These include inadequate governance and infrastructure, a lack of critical mass, insufficient one-on-one learning opportunities, limited access to mentors, lack of funding, and language barriers. Without overcoming these challenges, the 10/90 gap will remain in some disproportionate ratio, and there will be legitimate concerns about a stalled process towards independent science in the least resourced settings.^[10,11]

These shortcomings could potentially be addressed if each researcher and each research team had immediate access to a diverse network of multilingual scientific colleagues. Such a network could support researchers learn new methodologies, help them explore prospective research areas and write grants, engage with them in data analysis and interpretation, and assist with editing, translating and formatting.

There is hope. While not a panacea, by integrating generative AI-based large language model (LLM) chatbots into the research pipeline, a potential swarm of “scientific colleagues” may be available. They are massively scaleable,[12] and properly deployed, the chatbots could alleviate some of the existing constraints and expedite transformative change in research capacity in LMICs.

Over a year ago, OpenAI launched a publicly accessible, commercial LLM chatbot—ChatGPT.[13] It generated immediate interest in the scientific community, and over its first year, more than 1,600 articles about ChatGPT were indexed on PubMed.¹ The promise of and the concerns with the technology are quickly revealed by scanning early titles (including some in *Science* and *Nature*): “Abstracts written by ChatGPT fool scientists”,[14] “Can artificial intelligence help for scientific writing?”,[15] “ChatGPT Utility in Healthcare Education, Research, and Practice: Systematic Review on the Promising Perspectives and Valid Concerns”,[16] and “ChatGPT is fun, but not an author”.[17]

Since the launch of ChatGPT, a flurry of rivals have appeared. Google announced its competitor, Bard, in February 2023,[18] Anthropic released Claude to the public in July 2023,[19] and Microsoft integrated ChatGPT into the Bing search engine in July 2023.[20]

The technology is nascent, but preliminary work with LLM chatbots has already illuminated potential applications in enhancing research capacity, and the models are advancing rapidly. Enhancements include tutoring,[21] identifying research gaps,[22] supporting statistical coding,[23–25] interpreting statistical outputs, assisting in thematic analysis of text,[26] and drafting and editing sections of grant proposals,[27] reports, and manuscripts.[28,29] They have become part of the everyday workflow of many scientists.[28] Moreover, the facility of the LLM chatbots to operate across languages means that they can support researchers who face language barriers when engaging with the larger scientific community.[30,31] The technology allows scientists to develop their work and thinking in one language, or a mix of languages, and shift the results to a target language in the final stages.

Use cases

Appropriately integrated into RCS and the research pipeline, LLM chatbots could have a significant multiplier effect for LMIC researchers and their teams. The scalability of the technology means that anyone with internet access could have instant support, by their side, whenever they work. The support could be from quite low-level activities through to quite high-level thinking. Within the framework of Bloom’s educational taxonomy, LLMs can support researchers development from embedding factual knowledge about an area, including understanding relevant principles and theories (“knowing that”) through to the development and honing of procedural knowledge around subject specific methods and techniques (“knowing how”) right up to the meta-cognitive aspects of conceptualising new areas of research and critiquing the old.[32]

We have tested LLM chatbots in the following areas, and their extension to support RCS is obvious.

¹ chatGPT AND ("2022/11/30"[PDat]: "2023/11/29"[PDat])

- **Tutoring:** The LLM chatbots can explain and re-explain concepts in different ways to support understanding; they can provide clarification; and they can check and test understanding. They are immune to the irritation of repeated, stupid questions.
- **Conception and design:** LLM chatbots can help in refining research questions and designing research methodologies. Because the engagement with the chatbots is a “conversation” with a back-and-forth exchange, a researcher’s ideas can evolve and develop in a more natural way.
- **Data Management/Wrangling:** LLM chatbots can generate computer/statistical code, tidy-up existing code, insert comments into the code, identify errors in code, explain errors, and translate code between computer/statistical languages.
- **Comparing, contrasting, and summarising:** If they are provided with fulltexts, the chatbots can compare, contrast, and summarise content and style. They can identify the major themes and where texts agree and disagree.
- **Data analysis and interpretation:** they can interpret statistical results, and make intermediate and advanced analytical techniques accessible to researchers. Similarly, with qualitative data they can support coding and interpretation.[26]
- **Writing:** ChatGPT can assist researchers in the development of grant applications, reports, and manuscripts. They can generate, shorten, and reword text. They can edit drafts and ensure adherence to specific academic style guidelines. The chatbots can also shift the tone from informal to formal and change the frequency with which the passive voice is used, allowing researchers to develop outputs for different audiences.

English, as the lingua franca of scientific communication, poses a significant challenge to many researchers who are not native speakers.[33] LLM chatbots can facilitate the translation, editing, and proofreading of manuscripts. They can help prepare manuscripts for publication in English-language scientific journals, thus promote inclusivity and diversity in scientific research. They can also be used to summarise or translate English language articles, which would significantly reduce the time non-native English speaking researchers spend reading.

Limitations

We have, thus far, given the rosier interpretation of the value of LLM chatbots in RCS. There are, however, important limitations to their use. Principle among these is that LLM chatbots can produce garbage with confidence. They will assert falsehoods with the same certainty with which they assert truths. They have been known to hallucinate, make up references, confabulate facts, and generate garbage computer code.

They are imperfect, but their imperfections are not a reason not to use them. Like any tool, things go wrong when they are misused, but the value of LLM for RCS should not be diminished. There are, for instance, better and worse ways to phrase queries and “chats” to obtain helpful output.

Knowing enough to detect the moments of falsehood, or at least knowing enough to challenge it is essential.

The LLM chatbots are developed on a vast corpus of material drawn from the worldwide web. Any bias in the content of the web will also be coded into the chatbot. Some of these biases have been intentionally overridden, but any bias of which we are unaware will remain.

There will also be cost implications with using LLM chatbots. At the moment, there are freely available versions of various chatbots. As the value of the technology becomes more certain, so too will commercial value. In most cases, buying time on commercially available systems will be more cost effective than trying to establish new LLMs from scratch, but someone will need to pay for that. The question will then be about the cost-effectiveness of chatbots versus some alternative RCS strategy.

Chatbots in RCS

None of the limitations of LLMs speak against their integration into RCS or the research development pipeline. Rather, the limitations help to identify how the use of chatbots in RCS should evolve.

Realising the full potential of chatbots in RCS will require a strategic, evidence-based approach. First and foremost, providing training and guidelines for researchers on how to use chatbots effectively will be critical. To avoid the limitations of chatbots—like producing false information—researchers need to know the best practices for phrasing queries, validating outputs, and intelligently integrating chatbots into their workflows. Training resources and modules focused on chatbot literacy should be woven into existing RCS programs and platforms.

Rather than build entirely novel RCS initiatives around chatbots, integration into current programs will provide greater and faster returns on investment. For instance, chatbots could be incorporated as tutors into existing MOOCs, providing automated feedback. They could offer real-time support on literature reviews within virtual mentoring programs. Grant writing templates could be coupled with chatbots that iteratively strengthen draft proposals. Finding where chatbots can add value to established RCS pathways will ensure their thoughtful adoption and maximise their impact.

Any development and training should focus on high value activities first. While chatbots can assist with any stage of the research process, directing efforts toward those activities that bottleneck science for LMIC researchers should be targeted first. Standardising chatbot capacities for core research workflows, rather than diffuse applications, can enhance their utility.

Rigorously evaluating the effectiveness of chatbots for varied RCS contexts through comparative studies is needed to guide improvements in their use. While there is promise for the technology in RCS, hype must be tempered through objective assessments. Well designed evaluations and case studies can provide evidence on optimal chatbot uses and contexts in which more traditional RCS approaches should be preferred.

Finally, integrating chatbots into RCS risks deskilling researchers or losing human mentorship. These risks must be weighed and balanced. Chatbots should complement, not replace, core skill building and person-to-person exchange. Their scalability, however, could transform the RCS landscape. Avoiding over-automation and retaining balance will help chatbots genuinely expand research capacity, rather than undermine it. With prudent precautions and evidence-driven implementation, chatbots can play a major role in democratising research capacity strengthening.

Conclusion

Despite important strides over the past decades capacity to conduct independent and impactful science is still unequally distributed globally. Persistent gaps like limited access to training, mentors, computational resources, and language barriers threaten to increase inequities. Emerging generative AI systems, however, offer new opportunities to support research capacity strengthening (RCS) at scale.

Large language models like Claude and others demonstrate early promise in areas that could enhance the research endeavour, from interactive tutoring to writing assistance. Thoughtfully integrated into existing RCS programs, these AI chatbots can provide on-demand support for researchers, in multiple languages, to build skills, develop ideas, analyse data, and disseminate findings. While not without limitations, the technology holds disruptive potential if deployed strategically.

Realising this potential requires focusing efforts on integrating chatbots into high-value RCS functions, appropriate training to avoid pitfalls, and rigorous comparative evaluation to guide ongoing improvements. With prudent implementation guided by evidence, generative chatbots can provide LMIC researchers the ubiquitous aid of a personalized “scientific colleague” empowering the next generation of local innovation. Far from a panacea, chatbots nonetheless offer a timely new tool in service of the global democratisation of research capacity. Curbed of hype and harnessed strategically, they may help rewrite narratives of exclusion and inequity in science.

Authors

Daniel D. Reidpath, Institute for Global Health and Development, Queen Margaret University, Edinburgh, UK

Lucas Sempe, Institute for Global Health and Development, Queen Margaret University, Edinburgh, UK

Luciana Brondi, Institute for Global Health and Development, Queen Margaret University, Edinburgh, UK

Anna Thorson, TDR Research Capacity Strengthening Unit, WHO, Geneva, Switzerland

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